

eties. After 48-hours inoculation in a saturated-moisture atmosphere at 28-30°C, 40 seedlings of each variety were transplanted at 10 seedlings/pot. Pots

were placed under partly-shaded condition, 80-90% relative humidity, and temperature 28-30°C. At 30 days after inoculation, all varieties were infested

(see table). Seven varieties had severe infestations (disease incidence 61-78%); 24 varieties, moderate (45-60%); and three varieties, slight (26-39%). ■

Tungro-tolerant rice varieties for second crop

K. M. Balasubramaniam and N. Jaleel
Ahmed, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University
Regional Research Station, Aduthurai-
612101, Tamil Nadu, India

Normally second-crop rice in Thanjavur District, Tamil Nadu, is sown from 15 August to 30 September. The yields of 140- to 160-day varieties are adversely affected by epidemic rice tungro disease.

Four rice varieties — two Pankaji Jagannath (IET5852 and IET5897), one CR70-80-2/ Pankaj (IET5890), and one Pankaji Vijaya (IET6262) were compared to TN1 susceptible check and IR20 during 1979, a year when tungro occurred naturally, and 1980, a year when green jassids were kept under check (see table).

The parents of the hybrid derivatives

Grain yield and tungro disease score of 4 second-crop varieties, Tamil Nadu, India.^a

Variety	1979		1980	
	Grain yield (t/ha)	Tungro disease score	Grain yield (t/ha)	Tungro disease score
CR 70-80-2/Pankaj IET589 (CR213-1002)	3.4	5	4.8	3
Pankaj/Jagannath IET5852 (CR210-1005)	4.1	5	4.2	3
IET5897 (CR210-1009)	4.3	3	6.6	3
Pankaj/Vijaya IET6262 (CR262-16)	4.0	1	4.6	nil
TN1 (susceptible check)	0.5	9	0.7	9
IR20	2.2	5	3.8	3

^aScore chart scale (% hills infested):

- 1 less than 1%
- 3 about 10%
- 5 about 30%
- 9 about 100%

— Pankaj, CR70-80-2, Jagannath, and Vijaya — have tungro and green jassid resistance. IET5897 (CR210-1009 of Pankaj/Jagannath) consistently regis-

tered high yields during both years. The variety IET6262 (Pankaj/Vijaya) had a higher degree of field tolerance for rice tungro. ■

Evaluation of rice mutants resistance to thrip

M. A. Chowdhury and A. J. Miah, Institute of Nuclear Agriculture, P. O. Box 4, Mymensingh, Bangladesh

Rice thrip *Thrips oryzae* Williams is generally considered a minor pest of rice in Bangladesh. The only species so far recorded in Bangladesh, its populations recently have assumed economic significance in some areas. Infestations occur in early growth stages of rice plants. Both nymphs and adult thrips damage rice plants by lacerating the leaf-tip

Rice mutant resistance to thrip at Mymensingh, Bangladesh.

Mutant, variety	Leaf infestation ^a (%)	
	Summer 1981	Autumn, 1981
Mut 1-1	9.50 a	2.43 a
Mut 1-2	8.18 a	0.43 a
BR3	21.48 c	
IR8	19.02 bc	5.84 b
IRATOM24	18.59 bc	3.57 ab
IRATOM38	18.06 b	—

^aIn a column means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

tissues and sucking the sap. The infested plants appear to suffer from water stress. Infested leaves roll and yellow. In heavy infestations, the leaf-tips wither

and the plant wilts.

Two early-maturing mutants, Mut 1-1 and Mut 1-2 originally isolated from IR8 after gamma-irradiation, with the mother variety and checks BR3, IRATOM24, and IRATOM38 were assessed for rice thrip resistance. Experiments in summer and autumn, 1981, used a randomized block design with four replications. The infested leaves in 10 randomly selected hills in each plot were counted.

Mut 1-1 and Mut 1-2 were found to be moderately resistant to thrip, but varieties BR3, IR8, and IRATOM38 were susceptible (see table). ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Green leafhopper resistance and tungro infection in IR varieties

H. Rapusas and E. A. Heinrichs, The International Rice Research Institute

Varieties developed at the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) and evaluated by the seedling bulk test (SBT) exhibited different levels of *Nephotettix virescens* resistance. *N.*

virescens damages the rice plant directly and is a very efficient vector of rice tungro virus. To determine the degree of tungro resistance in varieties IR5 to IR54, 20-day-old seedlings of the test

Tungro infection in IR varieties, IRRI farm, April 1981.

varieties and TN1 as the susceptible check were transplanted in 2.2- × 1.2-m field plots at 20- × 20-cm spacing. A

row of tungro-infected TN1 seedlings planted around each plot served as a source of infection.

One week after transplanting, 100 *N. virescens* adults were caged on tungro-infected TN1 plants at the center of each plot. The insects were released 24 hours after caging. Treatments were replicated three times. Sixty days after release of the hoppers, tungro-infected hills were counted, and tungro infection was computed for each plot.

IR28, IR29, IR30, IR34, IR40, IR50, IR52, and IR54 had low levels of tungro infection (see figure). In general, varieties most resistant in the SBT also had the lowest tungro infection. In the IR varieties the degree of tungro infection in the field apparently is related to the degree of *N. virescens* resistance indicated by the SBT. ■

Response to insecticides of green leafhoppers from four sites in the Philippines

L. Fabellar, E. A. Heinrichs, and H. Rapugas, The International Rice Research Institute

To measure the development of insecticide resistance in green leafhoppers *Nephotettix virescens*, cultures collected from four sites in the Philippines were compared with a greenhouse culture. The insects originated from Pangasinan, Nueva Ecija, and Tarlac Provinces in Central Luzon.

Insecticide solutions of acephate, methyl parathion, MIPC, and monocrotophos were prepared. Three- to seven-day-old adult insects were anaesthetized and sprayed with 2 ml of the insecticide solution at rates of 0.125, 0.25, 0.4, 0.5, and 0.75 kg a.i./ha with a Potter's spray tower. Each treatment of 25 insects was replicated twice.

Treated insects were transferred to potted 2-week-old rice seedlings, covered with mylar cages (15.38 cm tall, 3.50 cm in diameter), and placed in 25° C to 27° C temperature, 60 to 80% relative humidity and 12 hours light. Mortality was recorded 48 hours after treatment and the computed lethal concentrations to kill 50% of the population (LC₅₀) were compared between colonies (see table).

Cultures from Palayan had 1.32-fold resistance to acephate and 2.02-fold re-

Resistance of field-collected green leafhoppers to insecticides (LC₅₀^a values). IRRI insectary, 1980.

Source of culture (Philippines)	Level of resistance ^b			
	Acephate	Methyl parathion ^c	MIPC	Monocrotophos
Palayan, Nueva Ecija	1.32 ^d	2.02 ^d	0.86	0.84
Santa Maria, Pangasinan	1.36 ^d	1.11	0.28	0.62
Rosales, Pangasinan	0.95	1.12	0.28	0.53
Pura, Tarlac	1.00	1.24	0.52	0.53

^aLC₅₀ = lethal concentration in kg a.i./ha applied in Potter's spray tower to kill 50% of the insect population. ^bLevel of resistance = $\frac{LC_{50} \text{ of field-collected culture}}{LC_{50} \text{ of greenhouse culture}}$. Resistance ratio of >1.0 indicates field culture resistance greater than greenhouse culture. ^cPENNCAP M formulation. ^dCultures with significantly higher (5% level) LC₅₀ values than the greenhouse culture.

sistance to methyl parathion. Cultures from Santa Maria had 1.36-fold resistance to acephate.

Methyl parathion and monocrotophos are probably the insecticides most

commonly used in the Philippines. The low level of resistance to the four insecticides indicates that resistance would not be a problem for farmers at the four sites. ■

Resistance of rice varieties to the green leafhopper in Southern India

S. Chelliah and A. M. Hanifa, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, India; and E. A. Heinrichs and G. S. Khush, International Rice Research Institute

Resistance of rice varieties to the green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) was studied in an international collaborative research project. Eleven varieties with known resistance genes, four varieties with unknown resistance genes, and resistant and susceptible checks were screened.

Test varieties were planted in seedboxes (60 × 40 × 10 cm) in 15 cm rows, replicated three times. Seedlings were

thinned to 30/ row 7 days after sowing. Seedboxes were infested with GLH adults (about 2/seedling), covered with nylon mesh cages, and maintained on galvanized on trays containing 6 cm water.

Damage rating began 6 days after infestation (DI) and continued to 11 DI. The 1-9 damage rating scale of the Standard Evaluation System for Rice was used. The rating at 9 DI, when 2 test varieties scored 8, was used to judge GLH resistance.

Moddai Karuppan with gene *Glh 7*, Ptb 8 with *glh 4*, and TAPL 796 with *Glh 6* had the highest levels of resistance (see table). ASD7 (*Glh 2*), IR8 (*Glh 3*), and ASD8 (*Glh 5*) were moderately resistant. Pankhari 203 (*Glh 1*) was